

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D5.2

Design, implementation and deployment of research object services – phase I

Grant agreement number	101017501
Start date of the project	Reliance
Duration of the project	24 months
Type of Action	Research and Innovation Action
Coordinator	PSNC

Due date of delivery	31/12/2021
Actual date of delivery	19/01/2022
Work package	WP5
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Responsible	PSNC
Reviewer	ESI
Version	1.0

This project has received funding from the European research infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017501

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History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Authors	Organization
0.1	20/11/2021	ToC	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.2	01/12/2021	Initial input – introduction	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.3	10/12/2021	Executive summary, scope, structure	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.4	15/12/2021	Section 5	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.5	20/12/2021	Section 6	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.6	29/12/2021	Section 7	Raul Palma, Malgorzata Wolniewicz	PSNC
0.7	30/12/2021	Section 3,4	Esteban Gonzalez, Oscar Corcho	UPM
0.8	4/1/2022	Updates in Section 1	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.9	7/1/2022	Bibliography, Acronyms, Review of all sections	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.95	14/1/2022	Document review	Jose Gomez Perez	ESI
0.96	16/1/2022	Section 2,3 updates	Esteban Gonzalez	UPM
0.97	17/1/2022	General improvements based on reviews	Raul Palma	PSNC
0.98	19/1/2022	Section 2,3 updates	Esteban Gonzalez	UPM
1.0	19/1/2022	Final formatting	Raul Palma	PSNC

Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management platform
API	Application Programming Interface
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
IAM	Identity and Access Management
Minim	Minimum information Model
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PyPI	Python Package Index
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RO	Research Object

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the implementation of the initial version of the tools and services for Research Objects (ROs) management, resulting from the WP5 tasks. In particular, such tools and services include the services for FAIR self-assessment and quality assessment of research objects, the adaptations of research objects evolution to EOSC scenarios, the initial integration of services from WP3 and WP4, and the current state of the user interfaces.

A key input for this deliverable and for the work carried out in the implementation of WP5 services is the vocabulary specification that is used in RELIANCE for the representation of the research objects, which has been implemented as an RO-crate profile as described in D5.1. A key characteristic of the proposed RO specification is that it is data-cube centric, as a fundamental differentiating principle of the Earth Science communities that are supported by RELIANCE. As described in D4.1, Data Cubes are becoming a reference service to provide a data access infrastructure and a reference set of tools for geospatial data management, mostly related to the access and exploitation of large collections of multi-temporal, multi-resolution satellite imagery at national/international scale. RELIANCE is leveraging data cubes to provide earth scientists with an efficient and scalable structured data access and discovery. Scientists are able to aggregate and describe data cubes in their research objects, and connect them with related resources (e.g., products generated, methods used for processing, publications generated, infrastructures used, etc.), in line with FAIR and open science principles.

2 Introduction

2.1 Scope

RELIANCE will extend the EOSC service offering with a set of industry-strong, innovative, interconnected services for the open, efficient, and cross-disciplinary management of the research lifecycle, adopting a holistic approach to address research activities in accordance with FAIR and Open Science principles. The core technology behind RELIANCE services is research objects, as the overarching information artefact to manage the research activities. Research objects, aka FAIR digital objects, are semantically rich aggregations of data, methods and people in scientific investigations supporting the implementation of FAIR guiding principles and the systemic change of science practices to Open Science. They describe and associate all of this content together in a machine-readable mechanism so that it can be more easily shared and exchanged. Research objects have been successfully applied by early adopter in Earth Science (see [1]), and in RELIANCE they will be further demonstrated in different multidisciplinary and vertical use cases in Earth Science. To that end, research objects rely in RELIANCE on Data Cubes for an efficient and scalable structured data access and discovery (see D4.2), as well as text mining services that extract machine-readable metadata from scholarly communications and Data Cube descriptions (see D3.2), providing researchers with means to discover scientific information at scale and structure their own research.

In RELIANCE, the core research object services are provided by the ROHub platform, while Data Cubes services are provided by the ADAM platform and the text mining services are provided by expert.ai technologies. These services are being interconnected to allow seamless access from different interfaces, using research objects as the main connecting point. Data Cubes can be linked in the research object as first-class entities but also described with a rich set of metadata (e.g., how it was generated or used). Text mining & enrichment services are being used to automatically enrich the research object with metadata extracted from the available annotations and textual resources aggregated in it, thus increasing their findability, interoperability and reuse.

Moreover, RELIANCE services have been onboarded in EOSC and they are being integrated or will reuse other EOSC services like those for authentication and identity management (EGI check-in), research data management, including services for depositing and sharing (B2DROP, B2SHARE, Zenodo), discovery and reuse (OpenAIRE Research Graph), and data management (Argos), as well as computing services (e.g., EGI Notebooks, EGI compute platform) as described in detail in Deliverable D6.1. Hence, RELIANCE acts as a bridge between other EOSC services, e.g., connecting data used by researchers, including Data Cubes for accessing Copernicus data and other data resources deposited in EOSC services (e.g., B2DROP, B2SHARE), the methods used to process such data (e.g., via EOSC Notebooks), and the final results published via scholarly communication services (e.g., Zenodo). Moreover, as part of the RO evolution, different snapshots/releases can be generated throughout the research lifecycle, so that they can be shared and published via research data platforms like B2SHARE and Zenodo for their long-term preservation and citation.

2.2 Audience

The target audience of this deliverable is manifold. Firstly, this document is intended to serve the RELIANCE Consortium, since it presents the set of services for using and managing research objects, which is particularly useful for the current user communities. The document also targets RELIANCE services providers and, more generally, developers of tools and services that may leverage or create research objects, as it describes the programmatic interfaces to use/integrate these services with other services. Additionally, this deliverable will be useful for other EOSC-related projects, since it will provide a description of the research objects services that have been onboarded and made available to other EOSC projects and in general to the EOSC community. Finally, the document will be useful for the open call that RELIANCE is launching in 2022 to attract new communities and extend the current ones, since it will provide a reference for them to use the research object services and tools.

2.3 Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 3 presents an overview of the RELIANCE RO-crate profile implementation (resulting from D5.1)
- Section 4 presents the ongoing work regarding guidelines and tools for FAIR assessment of research objects
- Section 5 presents the results and ongoing work regarding the community-driven quality assessment methods and tools.
- Section 6 presents the results and ongoing work regarding the mechanisms for the management of versioning and evolution of research objects, and their adaptation to EOSC scenarios.
- Section 7 presents the results and ongoing work regarding the integration and reuse of RELIANCE services and other EOSC services, and the interfaces developed to access research object functionalities.

3 RELIANCE RO-crate profile

RO-Crate¹ is a community created to define a lightweight specification for packaging research objects. This specification is based on schema.org² annotations in JSON-LD. Schema.org provides a vocabulary to describe structure data on the Internet. Concepts as Organizations, Persons, Digital Objects and Actions can be modeled in a standard vocabulary, as well as their associated metadata.

¹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

² <https://schema.org/>

RELIANCE members are part of the ro-crate initiative³ and have contributed to its specification process [2], [3].

The use of this specification reports some advantages:

- All the research objects are homogeneous.
- The research objects generated can be used by a wider community
- The research objects can be manipulated for other tools generated by the community. Some examples can be found here: <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/tools/>

The research objects used JSON-LD as format files. JSON-LD is designed to represent linked data on the Internet allowing in our case to express the relations between the different resources of a research object. Also, the use of this format facilitates the consumption of research objects for other services, it means, gives support to a M2M (Machine to Machine) model.

The specification selected to describe our research objects is 1.1 (the latest version of the specification).

According to RO-Crate, a research object has the following structure:

- RO-Crate Metadata file. This file must be written with the format JSON-LD 1.0 and has to be named like ro-crate-metadata.json. This metadata file is generated by the tool ACTION-ASSET (see next section). The resources that compound research objects, and relations between them must be described in this document.
- RO-Crate Website. In this case, a human readable version of the research object can be attached. In our case, this version is supported by the platform ROHub, where our ROs are shared.
- Payload files and directories. In the context of ACTION, our ROs are not created with the files inside them. All these resources are external, and they are published in repositories like Zenodo, YouTube, SlideShare, etc.

RO-Crate can model a huge variety of different ROs. RELIANCE adds a new type of RO named Data Cube centric research object. The definition of Data Cube is still missing, although the Open Geospatial Consortium is working on it. A Data Cube is designed for accessing to large volumes (and variety) of geospatial data. A Data Cube is a multi-dimensional concept and consists of a comprehensive set of functions that describes digital resources (see D4. 1)

The Data Cube services describe both the data structure (e.g., its spatial resolution or temporal dimensions and granularity), to all the available services to exploit discovery, access, view and analytics services. In summary, a Data Cube is a particular view (dataset) of a collection of data filtered by temporal and spatial dimensions.

According to the metadata model proposed for Data Cubes in D4.1, there is a coverage metadata layer in Data Cubes to cover these dimensions. It is composed of the following metadata fields.

- **Simple Geolocation** that represents the shape of the location (point, box and polygon).
- **Spatial coverage**, with additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, coordinate reference system)
- **Temporal coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit)
- **Vertical coverage**, with the following additional attributes: extent, step-resolution, reference system-unit)

³ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/community.html>

Coming back to RO-Crate, to model places and time, RO-Crate introduces the concept of **Contextual Entities**, which are entities that exist outside the digital sphere, such as locations, people and time. These contextual entities can be associated with data entities like dataset. For that, a data cube can be modeled as follows.

First, the place must be specified. Remember RO-Crate is based on schema.org so the attributes of this vocabulary can be used in our JSON-LD. To use a name of a place, for example Catalina Park, an identifier for the service geonames.org must be provided. This would be an example in RO-Crate:

```
{
  "@id": "http://sws.geonames.org/8152662/",
  "@type": "Place",
  "description": "Catalina Park is a disused motor racing venue, located at Katoomba ...",
  "geo": {
    "@id": "#b4168a98-8534-4c6d-a568-64a55157b656"
  },
  "uri": "https://www.geonames.org/8152662/catalina-park.html",
  "name": "Catalina Park"
},
```

Also, an specific location can be expressed with the type GeoCoordinates. In this case, the content of the JSON-LD should be:

```
{
  "@type": "GeoCoordinates",
  "name": "Catalina Park",
  "latitude": "43.088521",
  "longitude": "-79.072930",
  "name": "Latitude: 43.088521 Longitude: -79.072930"
},
```

To represent shapes, RO-Crate has the type GeoShape that can model a box, a circle, a line or a polygon.

Once a place is described, it must be linked to a Dataset. Remember that our Data Cubes are datasets at final. For that, we must use the attribute **contentLocation** inside the description of our dataset.

All these elements fulfill the spatial coverage requirements of our Data Cube centric RO, so there is no need to extend or add more elements to the specification of RO-Crate.

In the case of **Time coverage**, we can make use of the attribute **temporalCoverage** in the dataset entity. The values used in this field can be DateTime (specific time point) or a textual string indicating a time period (ISO 8601 format). For example, we can use the texts 2020/2021 or 2000 - 2021 to indicate periods of time. With this field, the temporal requirements of our Data Cube model can be covered.

Regarding **Vertical coverage**, both GeoCoordinates and GeoShape contain a field to describe the elevation of the location. The only missing part respecting the specification of the Data Cube model

is the related with the vertical coverage range. A particular elevation can be expressed but not a range of them, it means, we cannot model 3D objects. To express this, the specification of RO-Crate must be extended to represent multi-dimensional objects for places.

There are other layers in our Data Cube model that should be analyzed, the Data Acquisition and Product Information layer. The following table shows the metadata present in our Data Cube model and if they are present in RO-Crate.

The specification of the RELIANCE RO-Crate profile is published in the following link:

<https://reliance-eosc.github.io/reliance-ro-crate/>

A new vocabulary has been created to model the new metadata introduced by the concept Data Cube. This metadata was analyzed in - D5.1 RO model adapted to EOSC -, section 3.3, Table 2. These new terms are identified with the **prefix rel**. New terms are published on:

<https://raw.githubusercontent.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/ro-terms/master/earth-science/vocabulary.ttl>

4 Guidelines and tools for FAIR assessment of research objects

One of the objectives in RELIANCE is to make a research FAIR as much as possible. One of the obstacles to this task is to define and to assess the FAIRness of a research, in our case, the FAIRness of a research object. For it, RELIANCE will deploy a service to assess the FAIRness of a research object, analyzing the existing guidelines and tools used to this task. But first, what is the meaning of FAIR?

Although the term of FAIR has been associated to data, more initiatives are appearing to apply it to other objects. We can find the term FAIR Digital Object [4], where objects represent data, software, protocols and other research resources. All these resources are aggregated in a research object.

FAIR is the acronym of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, and in the context of data [5]:

- Data are **Findable** when (meta)data has a global, unique and persistent identifier. Additionally, data must be described with which metadata and it must be indexed or registered in a searchable resource.
- **Accessible** data objects can be reached (by humans and machines) using free and standard protocols. These protocols can be supported by authorization and authentication procedures, if necessary. One important feature is that the metadata must be always present, even the data have been removed from the repository
- **Interoperable** data objects are resources that are described following a vocabulary and use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. This allows to share easily the information between objects and make your objects consumable by machines.
- **Reusable** data objects have a clear data usage license.

In the context of Earth Science, there is initiative of the project ROHub to assess the FAIRNESS of a research object [1]. ROHub provides tools for generating DOIs for your ROs, a searchable engine, semantic annotations for vocabularies and the use of licenses.

A research object is an aggregation of research resources. An interesting point is that all these resources are packed inside the RO. It means that when we define the FAIRness of a RO, we must

analyze the FAIRness of each resource. It includes datasets, software, notebooks and other research resources.

The standard RO-Crate, adopted by RELIANCE, allows us to express the elements we need to make our resource FAIR. The only point to consider is whether the resources are internal or external. Internal means that the resource is packed inside the RO, so it shares the PID with the RO. External means that the resource is published in an external repository and is linked into the RO. The first approach can be problematic because the resource can't have a Persistent Identifier (PID), making it not findable. This is not the case of RELIANCE because each resource linked in the platform ROHub has a PID mint with the service provided by w3id⁴. Also, a DOI can be created if the researcher deems it necessary

4.1 Guidelines

There are no specific guidelines to build FAIR Research Objects. Nevertheless, there are some studies about how to make your research FAIR [1] and guidelines of fairification of specific resources present in a RO such as data and software. Thus, RELIANCE will work in a guideline to produce FAIR Research Objects, unifying the existing criteria. This will be benefit to scientists that work with Research Objects and want to make their research FAIR. Potentially, this resource will be able to use in further developments in ROHub to check the FAIRness of the ROs.

In the case of data, the fairification process⁵ is well defined by the project GO FAIR⁶ can be followed. It is composed of seven steps.

1. **Access to the non-FAIR-data**
2. **Analyze the data**, identifying their structure and the relation between their elements
3. **Define the semantic model**. This model describes the entities and their relationships. It should be based on existing ontologies and vocabularies. Remember that RO-Crates provides vocabularies to model ROs.
4. **Make data linkable**. It is needed to transform these data into linked data using the semantic model defined in step 3. Remember that RO-Crates use JSON-LD format, which makes it linked data by default.
5. **Assign license**. It is important to assign a license to our data to make our data reusable.
6. **Define metadata for the dataset**, providing enough rich metadata.
7. **Deploy FAIR data resource**, publishing it in public repositories and indexing their metadata in search engines.

Software used in a research also is included in a RO. In this context, the project fair-software has designed a collection of recommendations⁷.

1. **Use a publicly accessible repository with version control**. One of the most popular is GitHub.
2. **Add a license**. This license can be open (Creative Commons) or with copyright. Remember to specify the terms and conditions in your license.
3. **Register your code in a community registry**.
4. **Enable citation of the software**. In this case, our software must have a DOI and a text that specifies how to cite it. Zenodo is a good resource to make your software citable.

⁴ <https://w3id.org/>

⁵ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/fairification-process/>

⁶ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

⁷ <https://fair-software.eu/recommendations/repository>

5. Use a software quality checklist.

Plus, these recommendations, the study *Towards FAIR principles* [6] provides a list of recommendations for FAIR software, re-writing the principles defined by the publication of FAIR principles [3].

4.2 Tools

There are some tools that are currently working in the FAIR assessment task and that they can be used to build our service.

FAIR-Aware⁸ is an online tool to assess how the researchers know about the FAIR process. The objective is to use it before uploading data to the repository. It is based on an online questionnaire composed of 10 questions. It is a learning tool.

FAIRsFAIR Data Objects Assessment Metrics⁹. It is a list of 17 metrics used to assess the FAIRness of data. It is designed as a checklist to verify if your data is following the FAIR principles.

F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool¹⁰. It is a REST service to assess the FAIRness of your data based on 16 of the 17 metrics defined in the FAIRsFAIR Data Objects Assessment Metrics. It used web standards and it is connected with external registries such as r3data, DataCite and Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV). A demo can be found at: <https://www.f-uji.net/>

HowFairIs¹¹ is a project to analyze GitHub and Gitlab repositories in compliance with the recommendations given by the project fair-software.eu. Also, analyze other practices such as presence of documentation, code quality, code coverage of unit tests and publication of docker images in DockerHub.

SOMEF¹² (**Software Metadata Extraction Framework**) is a project to extract relevant information from README files. It includes citation, installation instructions, usage examples, requirements, license, DOI, DockerFile, Notebooks, keywords, etc. A complete list is available online¹³. SOMEF uses the Software Description Ontology¹⁴. The tool uses supervised classifiers, header analysis and regular expressions to retrieve all these files.

FOOPS[7] is a tool (beta version) to assess the FAIRness of ontologies. It is based in the recommendations given by the project FAIRsFAIR, but adapting them to semantic artifacts (ontologies).

1.1 FAIR assessment service

The objective of this service is to deploy a service to assess the FAIRness of a Research Object. This service will be used by the platform RO-Hub or any platform or user that requires. We will analyze the possibility to include it into the EOSC Marketplace. This service will be **RO-Crate compatible** and will be use the standards of **REST services** to make it as usable as possible.

⁸ <https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl/>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3775793>

¹⁰ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>

¹¹ <https://github.com/fair-software/howfairis/>

¹² <https://github.com/KnowledgeCaptureAndDiscovery/somef/>

¹³ <https://somef.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

¹⁴ <https://w3id.org/okn/o/sd>

Our service not only takes into account the FAIRness of the research object in general, but each of the resources of which it is composed. This service will consider the resources with type: data, software and publications although more types of the resources such as workflows or ontologies will be included in the future. For it, the service will be designed for this purpose with a modular structure. Figure 1 depicts the structure of this service, where it can be observed that is an aggregation of specific services.

Figure 1: FAIR service structure

One of the first steps of our service’s development will be the creation of a guideline to define the FAIRness of a Research Object. This includes new metrics based on the metrics defined by the FAIRsFAIR project and adapted to the different kind of resources to assess.

The interface of the service will be based on FOOPS and we will explore the integration of external services like FUJI, either in external endpoints or internal endpoints (own deployment). This service will generate the following products.

1. Guideline to build Research Objects
2. Definition of the service API
3. FAIR data deployment service. As it has been commented, this service could be covered by the service FUJI developed by the project FAIRsFAIR
4. FAIR software service
5. FAIR publications service
6. FAIR Research Object service

5 Community-driven quality assessment

RELIANCE aims to produce not only FAIR research objects, as described in the previous section, but also research objects of high quality according to what the research communities producing and reusing them consider relevant. Such quality assessment aims to provide, thus, an indication of the fitness of the research object in that particular community, typically by assessing a number of quality dimensions, such as accuracy, completeness, or availability.

To make such assessments, RELIANCE draw upon the idea of checklists, a well-established tool for ensuring safety, quality and consistency in complex operations, such as manufacturing or critical

care [8, 9]. A checklist explicitly defines a list of requirements that must be fulfilled or assessed for a given task. Accordingly, RELIANCE is providing the mechanisms and tools to support the assessment of research objects quality following a community driven approach, where the needs and expectations of researchers in the community with respect to what makes research (re-)usable are translated and formalized into a set of quality checks.

To achieve this, RELIANCE is extending and adapting existing research object quality assessment technology based on checklists (called RO-manager [10]), which check e.g., whether certain datasets are accessible, that appropriate and complete metadata facilitating its reuse is available or that a computational service is available. Such technology relies on the Minim ontology¹⁵ [11] (see Figure 2) to express quality requirements as RDF, and an assessment service to evaluate the conformance of target research object against a Minim checklist.

In RELIANCE, the checklist service is being adapted and extended to interact efficiently with the latest ROHub (research object management) platform, to support RELIANCE metadata models and vocabularies (aligned with EOSC), as well as to enable an easy customization of checklist to community needs on top of automated quality checking mechanisms. Additionally, new checklists are being created to reflect the current RELIANCE community's needs. Furthermore, RELIANCE is providing means for monitoring the quality over time, generating alerts when there is a decay, so researchers can take appropriate measures.

Finally, to facilitate the assessment and generation of high-quality research objects, RELIANCE will provide appropriate interfaces not only to assess but also to correct/improve the quality of the research object in a user-friendly manner, so that it remains available for reuse and preservation. The availability of these mechanisms for the research community will encourage the growing adoption of reproducible practices in research management.

¹⁵ <http://purl.org/minim/description>

Figure 2 Minim data model

5.1 Checklist service Integration with ROHub

ROHub is the RELIANCE service providing the research object management functionalities. As part of RELIANCE, ROHub 2.0 has been released and deployed. As described in detail in Section 7, ROHub’s new architecture comprises a backend component exposing a RESTful API, an IAM component, (meta-) data and resource storage components and a set of user interfaces. Additionally, various external services are integrated with ROHub, including the checklist service that provides the research object (RO) quality assessment functionalities. The checklist service¹⁶ exposes a simple REST API to assess the RO quality comprising two GET methods:

- /trafficlight_json: return the evaluation result in JSON format
- /trafficlight_html: return an HTML representation of the result.

Both methods receive three parameters as input:

- Research object, is the target RO to be evaluated
- Minim, is the particular checklist to be used for the evaluation. This checklist is an RDF document expressing the desired quality requirements to be checked based on the minim model (cf. Figure 2).
- Purpose, is the specific purpose in the checklist document to be used for the assessment. The purpose allows to group quality to conditions to check specific characteristics or features in a research object, e.g., completeness, accessibility, ready to release, etc. A

¹⁶ <https://sandbox.rohub.org/roevaluate2/evaluate/>

checklist document may have multiple purposes, a purpose group multiple conditions, and a condition may be part of multiple purposes.

Internally, the checklist service contacts ROHub to retrieve the target RO's manifest and all the aggregated annotation bodies, which are used to build the full RO graph that is used as source for assessing the quality conditions. Each quality condition is then transformed into a SPARQL query that is assessed over the generated graph. Additionally, if the quality check requires assessing if an aggregated resource is accessible (e.g., an external service or data source), the checklist service retrieves from ROHub the resource location and checks if it can access it or not.

In order to integrate the checklist service with the latest ROHub API, both the checklist service¹⁷ and the ROHub required some changes, including the indexing of RO's manifest and annotation bodies in the Elasticsearch index to speed up their access from the checklist service, an improved management of http sessions in the checklist service, and the addition of namespaces in checklist service to support the RELIANCE metadata model elements in the quality conditions, including:

- "sch": "https://schema.org/"
- "pav": "http://purl.org/pav/"
- "rel1", "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/earth-science#"

To access the checklist services functionalities, ROHub exposes them transparently to the user via its user interfaces. Hence, ROHub users won't need to change interface or use another tool to assess the quality of their research objects. Access through the user interfaces (portal, library) is still under development. In ROHub portal this functionality will be available from the quality tab of the research object visualization (like in the previous ROHub), as depicted in described in Section 7.

As part of the future work, we are evaluating mechanisms enabling an easy customization of checklists to community needs. The goal is that researchers will be able to create/customize their own checklists, without previous knowledge of minim data model or implementation details, and use them to assess their research objects' quality. For this task, RELIANCE will also evaluate and leverage existing tools like mkminim¹⁸ and RightField¹⁹.

5.2 RELIANCE checklists

The requirements collected and distilled from the RELIANCE research communities include, among others, a simplified list of research object types and simplified checklists for each of these types (see Section 5 in D7.1 for further details). The types of research objects were limited to the following:

- Bibliographic centric RO
- Data centric RO (including Data Cube)
- Executable RO (including Jupyter Notebooks)
- Basic RO

Based on those types, the communities agreed on the following set of quality checks. The common checks are:

- RO has a title
- RO has a description
- RO has a creator
- RO has publisher information
- RO has a subject (research area)

¹⁷ The latest version of checklist service is available at <https://github.com/rapw3k/ro-manager>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/wf4ever/ro-manager/blob/master/src/checklist/mkminim.md>

¹⁹ <https://rightfield.org.uk/>

- RO has a sketch
- RO has keywords
- The RO aggregates at least one resource
- The resources aggregated by the RO have a type
- Optionally, the RO may have authors defined for credits
- Optionally, the RO may have contributors defined for credits
- Optionally, the RO may have geolocation associated

Additionally, for a Bibliographic-centric RO:

- there is at least a resource in “biblio” folder

For a Data-centric RO:

- there is at least a resource in “raw data” folder
- there is at least a resource in “data” folder
- there is at least a resource in “metadata” folder

For an Executable RO:

- there is at least a resource in “input” folder
- there is at least a resource in “tool” folder
- there is at least a resource in “output” folder

Accordingly, we have generated four different checklists. One for the basic RO type, which has the common checks, and one for each of the other types (bibliographic-centric, data-centric, executable) which include the common checks plus the type specific conditions. A snippet of the basic checklist implementation is provided in the table below²⁰.

²⁰ The full checklist can be downloaded via: <https://box.psnc.pl/f/1e5c2d93d4/%3fraw=1>

Table 1 Basic RO checklist snippet

```

<minim:Model rdf:about="#experiment_complete_model">
  <rdfs:label>Complete experiment</rdfs:label>
  <rdfs:comment>
    This model defines information that must be satisfied by the target RO
    for the target RO to be considered a complete and fully-described experiment.
  </rdfs:comment>
  ## MUST
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_title"   />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_description" />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_creator"   />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_publisher" />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_subject"   />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_at_lease_one_resource" />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_sketch"    />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_has_keywords"  />
  <minim:hasMustRequirement   rdf:resource="#RO_resources_have_type" />
  ## OPTIONAL
  <minim:hasMayRequirement    rdf:resource="#RO_has_authors"   />
  <minim:hasMayRequirement    rdf:resource="#RO_has_contributors" />
  <minim:hasMayRequirement    rdf:resource="#RO_has_geolocation" />
</minim:Model>

<!-- RO title is present -->
<minim:Requirement rdf:about="#RO_has_title">
  <minim:isDerivedBy>
    <minim:ContentMatchRequirementRule>
      <minim:forall>
        <ro rdf:type ro:ResearchObject, ore:Aggregation .
          FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?ro rdf:type ore:AggregatedResource }
          FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?ro rdf:type roterms:WorkflowRunBundle }
        </minim:forall>
      <minim:exists>
        ?ro dcterms:title|sch:title ?rotitle .
      </minim:exists>
      <minim:showpass>Research Object has title</minim:showpass>
      <minim:showfail>Research Object does not have title, , including <i>%</i>(ro)s </i>.
      You must add annotation: title (dcterms or schema vocabulary)</minim:showfail>
      <minim:derives rdf:resource="#RO_has_title" />
    </minim:ContentMatchRequirementRule>
  </minim:isDerivedBy>
  <minim:seq>001</minim:seq>
</minim:Requirement>

```

5.3 Sample checklist evaluation

As an example, below we provide the evaluation result of assessing the quality of one of the research objects from the supersites community using the basic checklist created based on RELIANCE requirements (for the purpose ready-to-release). The checklist API call is as follows:

https://sandbox.rohub.org/roevaluate2/evaluate/trafficlight_json?RO=https://w3id.org/ro-id/3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8&minim=https://box.psnr.pl/f/1e5c2d93d4/%3fraw=1&purpose=ready-to-release

The result of call with a truncated description is presented below:

Table 2 sample checklist evaluation result

```

{ "rouri": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8/"
, "roid": "3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8"
, "title": "Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM"
, "description": "The VSM (Volcano and Seismic source Modelling) tool is a Fortran code used to model ground deformation detected by the most common geodetic techniques (interferometric SAR, GPS, leveling and EDM - Electro-optical Distance Measuring)..Contact: Elisa Trasatti elisa.trasatti@ingv.it."
, "checklisturi": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#experiment_complete_model"
, "checklistpurpose": "ready-to-release"
, "checklisttarget": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8/"
, "checklisttargetid": "3a05b7d2-a107-4274-9b7a-be8c543136b8"
, "checklisttargetlabel": "Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM"
, "evalresult": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#potentiallySatisfies"
, "evalresultlabel": "does not satisfy"
, "evalresultclass": ["fail", "must"]
, "checklistitems":
[ { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_title"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has title"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_description"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has description"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_creator"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has creator"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_publisher"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object does not have publisher. You must add annotation: publisher (dcterms or schema vocabulary)"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": false
, "itemclass": ["fail", "must"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_subject"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has subject"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_at_least_one_resource"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object aggregates at least one resource"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_sketch"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has sketch"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_keywords"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has keywords"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_resources_have_type"
, "itemlabel": "Aggregated resources have a type"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMustRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_authors"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object does not have author(s) (credit of its content). You should add annotation: authoredBy (pav vocabulary) "
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMayRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": false
, "itemclass": ["fail", "may"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_contributors"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object does not have contributor(s) (credit of its content). You should add annotation: contributedBy (pav vocabulary) "
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMayRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": false
, "itemclass": ["fail", "may"]
}, { "itemuri": "https://box.psncl.pl/seafhttp/files/43b124de-bb04-45f6-9ffb-865df016fc80/basicRO-reliance-checklist.rdf#RO_has_geolocation"
, "itemlabel": "Research Object has geometry"
, "itemlevel": "http://purl.org/minim/minim#hasMayRequirement"
, "itemsatisfied": true
, "itemclass": ["pass"]} ] ]

```

5.4 Quality monitoring

Research objects (ROs) are monitored through quality metrics such as completeness, stability, and reliability [12]. Completeness measures the extent to which a research object satisfies a number of requirements specified in a checklist, stability measures the degree to which the research object completeness remains unchanged, and reliability combines the previous metrics to provide a unique value indicating to what extent the research object is complete and how stable it has been historically. These values are calculated taking into consideration a checklist of quality requirements to be satisfied. The monitoring of ROs is carried out by the stability service, another added value integrated with ROHub.

The stability service exposes a REST API and a notification feed, via the following methods:

- /exec-checklist: Runs a checklist evaluation on a RO and saves it in the database
 - **Method:** POST
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] AND Optional: checklist=[alphanumeric]
 - **Response codes:** Created (201), Bad Request (400), INTERNAL SERVER ERROR (500)
- /completeness: Gets the completeness quality metric for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: date=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:** [double]
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Not Found (404), Bad Request (400)
- /stability: Gets the stability quality metric for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:** [double]
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Not Found (404), Bad Request (400)
- /reliability: Gets the reliability quality metric for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:** [double]
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Not Found (404), Bad Request (400)
- /quality-time-series: Gets the time series of the calculated quality metrics for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:**

Table 3 Response from quality-time-series

```
[{
  "rouri": [alphanumeric],
  "roid": [alphanumeric],
  "evaldate": [date],
  "stabilitystartdate": [date],
  "stabilityenddate": [date],
  "completeness": [double],
  "stability": [double],
  "reliability": [double],
  "checklistitems": [
    {
      "itemuri": [alphanumeric],
      "itemlabel": [alphanumeric],
      "itemlevel": [alphanumeric],
      "itemsatisfied": [boolean]
    },
    ...
  ]
},
...]
```

- /notifications: Gets the Atom notifications of the calculated quality metrics changes for a RO
 - **Method:** GET
 - **Parameters:** Required: ro=[alphanumeric] OR Optional: from=[yyyy-mm-dd] OR Optional: to=[yyyy-mm-dd]
 - **Response:** Atom feed
 - **Response codes:** OK (200), Bad Request (400)

6 Evolution mechanisms

ROHub enables the management of versioning and evolution of research objects. The evolution or lifecycle of the research object (RO) comprises all the stages that the RO transitions from its conception until its conclusion. Different lifecycles scenarios were identified and analyzed in previous projects (e.g., Wf4Ever, EVEREST). Based on that analysis the possible RO states were derived (see Figure 3) and implemented in ROHub:

- **Live ROs:** represent a work in progress. They are thus mutable as the content or state of their resources may change.
- **Snapshot ROs:** are intended as a record of past activity, ready to be disseminated as a whole. They are immutable, and reflect the state of the Live RO at a certain time.
- **Archived ROs:** represent the final stage of a RO where it has either reached a version that the author prescribes to be stable and meaningful and is appropriate for publication and long-term preservation, or it has been deprecated. They are therefore immutable, with no further changes or versions allowed.
- **Forked ROs:** throughout the research object lifecycle, new lines of work can be started at any point in time (e.g., to explore different hypothesis, test different configurations), either while the research object is alive by forking the Live RO at some point in time, or once the RO has reached a milestone/stable state by forking any of the RO snapshots or the RO archive.

Figure 3 Research Object Lifecycle States

An important challenge previously addressed was to support the assignment of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) to research objects that are ready for publication during their lifecycle. This is particularly relevant for researchers, as it is the most typical mechanism used to cite research outputs, e.g., papers, datasets, etc. Hence, in order to allow citation of research objects, which can also count for the researcher academic score, it was important for ROHub to be able to generate a DOI for a research object. Accordingly, ROHub became a Datacite²¹ DOI service provider.

The envisioned scenario is that once the researcher(s) consider that the LIVE research object on which they are working has reached some milestone and its content is worth of publication or sharing, for instance as a technical report for internal distribution or as scholar contribution to the research community, they can proceed to generate a SNAPSHOT, which as mentioned before is a copy at a certain point in time of a LIVE research object. SNAPSHOTS are good candidates to receive a DOI since, according to the definition, they are immutable and ready to be shared. It will be up to the scientist to decide if they want to assign a DOI when they generate a SNAPSHOT, and up to the research object management platform (ROHub) to verify that the research object fulfils the requirements, drawn from the research object checklist, to get it.

Similarly, when the researcher(s) consider the investigation to be final the research object is ARCHIVED. This is the state for research objects that have reached a high maturity degree such that its content is not going to be modified, and in such case also a good candidate for having a DOI, or that have been deprecated (e.g., research line stopped or found useless). Note that in a typical scenario, a LIVE research object gives rise to a number of SNAPSHOT research objects before producing an ARCHIVED research object.

²¹ <https://datacite.org/>

Furthermore, throughout the research object lifecycle, new lines of work can be started at any point in time (e.g., to explore different hypothesis, test different configurations), either while the research object is alive by forking the LIVE RO at some point in time, or once the RO has reached a milestone/stable state by forking an RO SNAPSHOT or an RO ARCHIVE (see Figure 3). The FORK(ed) RO is a subtype of LIVE RO, and thus it works in the same way, i.e., A SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE can be generated from a FORK RO, and thus assigned a DOI.

As part of RELIANCE, the lifecycle has been further extended in order to leverage and reuse existing EOSC services. The goal was to allow the publication of shareable research objects (i.e., SNAPSHOTS/ARCHIVES) in general/popular EOSC repositories like Zenodo or B2Share, which could contribute to their dissemination, increasing their findability and potential reuse (i.e., their FAIRness). The research object is published in those repositories in the form of an RO-crate, which is the current standard method to capture and describe the research object using structured metadata²² (see D5.1). Moreover, RO-crate has been agreed as the exchange format of research objects with other people in the community, including representatives of OpenAire (Zenodo).

Hence, in order to support the previous scenario, ROHub provides now the user with different options when generating a SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE:

- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE with a DOI provided by ROHub and publish it in Zenodo and/or B2Share
- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE and publish it in Zenodo and/or B2share, which will generate a DOI for it
- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE with a DOI provided by ROHub without publishing it somewhere else
- Generate the SNAPSHOT/ARCHIVE without DOI or publishing it somewhere else.

As part of the next steps, additional options will be supported during the research object lifecycle:

- Integrate ROHub with additional EOSC services, in particular B2Drop, which the user will be able to choose as the default storage location for the internal resources added and aggregated by the research object during its lifecycle.
- Support additional operations during the lifecycle, such as the merging and/or creation of pull requests from research object forks to their original research object
- Support additional publishing repositories, such as GitHub.

The latest features to the research object lifecycle management, including the future work are depicted in Figure 4. ROHub interfaces to evolution features are described in Section 7.

²² <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/1.1/introduction.html>

Figure 4 Research Object Lifecycle State with RELIANCE features

7 Integration and access

ROHub [13, 14] is the main service in RELIANCE providing the research object management functionalities. It is a holistic solution for the storage, lifecycle management and preservation of scientific investigations, campaigns and operational processes via research objects. As part of RELIANCE, a new and enhanced ROHub²³ is being released, integrating new and/or updated services, including RO added value services (e.g., coming from WP3 and WP4), as well as EOSC services that are being leveraged and reused. This will enable, for example, the automatic enrichment of research objects with metadata extracted from the aggregated unstructured textual content, or the aggregation of Data Cubes, along with detailed metadata, in the research object to access large structured datasets (like Copernicus data). Additionally, ROHub provides the user interfaces to access all the latest research objects functionalities, including a reference Web Portal and a Python library that can be used, for instance, via Jupyter Notebooks. A high-level view of the new ROHub architecture, including the underlying technologies, is depicted in Figure 5.

As depicted in the figure, ROHub’s architecture comprises a backend component, an IAM component, (meta-) data and resource storage components and a set of user interfaces. Additionally, various external services are integrated with ROHub, including the checklist service and quality monitoring tool (see Section 5), the Enrichment service (WP3), a PDF service, as well as EOSC services.

In the following sections we describe each of these components more in detail.

²³ <https://reliance.rohub.org/>

Figure 5 ROHub high-level architecture

7.1 ROHub backend

The ROHub backend is the main service exposing all the research object management functionalities through a comprehensive RESTful API. The service has been implemented using Django (Python-based) web framework²⁴, Django REST framework for building the API²⁵, and Varnish Cache as HTTP accelerator²⁶. In RELIANCE there are two instances of ROHub backend: the production instance has deployed the latest stable version of the service and has all the real research objects stored, while the development instance has deployed the ongoing additions/updates that are being tested before moving them to a stable version and has only test research objects stored.

The service is available at:

- <https://api.rohub.org/api/> (production). (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psnec.pl/api/> (development)

²⁴ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

²⁵ <https://www.django-rest-framework.org/>

²⁶ <https://varnish-cache.org/>

Figure 6 ROHub backend service API entry point

The service can be tested via Swagger at:

- <https://api.rohub.org/api/swagger/> (production) (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/api/swagger/> (development)

Figure 7 ROHub backend service API Swagger interface

A detailed documentation is available via Redoc.

- <https://api.rohub.org/api/redoc/> (production) (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/api/redoc/> (development)

The screenshot displays the Redoc documentation for the `ros_create` endpoint. On the left, a sidebar lists various services, with `ros_create` selected. The main area shows the endpoint details, including its method (`POST`), path (`/ros/`), and request body schema (`application/json`). The schema defines fields like `title`, `description`, `access_mode`, `type`, `template`, and `research_areas`. On the right, the 'Request samples' section shows a JSON payload for creating a Basic Research Object. Below it, the 'Response samples' section shows a `201` status code.

Figure 8 ROHub backend service redoc documentation

7.2 ROHub IAM

The ROHub Identity and Access Management (IAM) is based on Keycloak technology. It allows users to authenticate to ROHub and enables the single sign-on across different RELIANCE services. The most important feature of ROHub IAM is that is integrated with EOSC AAI. In particular it allows the user to authenticate using EGI check-in service. There are two instances of ROHub IAM: the production instance integrated with production EGI check-in and having the official set of ROHub users, and the development instance integrated with development EGI check-in and having test users.

The service is available at:

- <https://login.rohub.org/> (production)
- <https://keycloak-dev.apps.paas-dev.psncl.pl/auth/realms/rohub/account/> (development)

The figure below depicts the ROHub login page to authenticate through the selected Keycloak instance. From there, the user can authenticate via the EGI check-in service or by providing directly his email and password.

If the user selects to login with EGI check-in, then (s)he can use any of the identity providers supported by EGI check-in service (see Figure 10), such as its academic institution or one of the social account providers (e.g., orcid, google, Facebook, GitHub, LinkedIn, etc.). After selecting the academic/social identity provider, the user should follow the normal process of the provider to authenticate, providing its username/email and their password. If the user chooses to provide his email and password directly on ROHub login page, (s)he should provide its password in ROHub (not their academic/social account password).

Figure 9 ROHub login page

Figure 10 EGI check-in login page

Once the user is logged in, (s)he will be able to see and/or edit his/her user account settings in ROHub The figure below depicts the entry point to the user account settings, which includes the following sections:

- Account information, which includes all the user account fields that can be saved in ROHub, i.e., salutation, first name, last name, affiliation, description, areas of interest, user token in Zenodo, user token in B2Share and Orcid.

Figure 11 ROHub account settings

- Change password: This section enables the user to change the password of his/her account in ROHub. This password is independent of the EGI check-in password.
- Authenticator: ROHub AIM allows the user to save the device as a second level authentication. This is done through third party authentication applications (e.g., FreeOTP, Google Authenticator). The application scans the barcode provided in the user's account and generates an OTP which along with the name of the device can be saved.
- Federated identities: This section shows the user identity in EGI check-in, if any, which is essentially the username of the user in EGI.
- Sessions: Shows the current sessions for the user account. The session record consists of information like the user IP address, the start and end time of the session etc.
- Applications: This section shows the IAM application clients that this user is able to use to authenticate in ROHub, along with the roles and permissions associated to this account. The client used is generally transparent to the user, as it is set internally by the application itself (e.g., ROHub portal, ROHub python library, Enrichment service, etc.).

- Log: This section shows all the available activity log for the user account in ROHub, including the date of the event, type of the event (i.e., login), IP source, application client used, and any additional information like the username and authentication method used.

7.3 *Meta(data) storage and index*

ROHub uses different storage systems to store metadata and indexes. In particular, it uses:

- Virtuoso triplestore²⁷: stores all the research object metadata and annotations as RDF triples represented according the RO core model and vocabularies²⁸. Accordingly, the RO is described by a manifest, which includes RO metadata along with the resources aggregated, which can be resources (internal or external), folders and annotations about the RO and those resources. Each annotation has an associated body (also aggregated), which includes the actual metadata (e.g., RO title, RO description, type of resource, etc.). Similarly, each folder has an associated manifest with the list of resources it contains. This model provides a lot of flexibility and scalability in terms of the metadata that can be associated to the RO and its aggregated resources. In Virtuoso, each RO has one named graph for its manifest and one for each annotation body aggregated. Note that although internally ROHub uses the RO model to represent and describe ROs, it uses RO-crate as the default exchange format for research objects, e.g., to publish them in Zenodo/B2Share. Hence, ROHub internally maps the RO model to the RO-crate specification.
- PostgreSQL²⁹: stores information about the internal functioning of ROHub. This is the default storage for Django model objects, and thus it includes information of the research objects (a subset of the RDF metadata), about the resources (a subset of the RDF metadata), about the users (a sub set of keycloak information), etc. Additionally, PostgreSQL stores some technical data (not needed in the triplestore) that is necessary for ROHub execution like information whether a research object was cloned (e.g., as part of a snapshot/archive/fork generation), information about readers and editors of a research object, their quality information, likes/dislikes, ratings and comments associated.
- Elasticsearch³⁰: stores all the indexes in ROHub that are used to speed up the access to commonly used information, such as research objects (with a subset of the RDF metadata), users (a subset of the RDF metadata), organizations, the RO's manifests and annotation bodies. Additionally, the indexes include information imported from external systems like Zenodo regarding existing licenses openly available, in addition to custom ones added by the users.

Each ROHub instance has its own metadata storages and indexes. Hence, currently there are two instances for each of those services, one for ROHub production and one for ROHub development.

7.4 *Resources storage*

A research object can aggregate both internal and external resources. For the latter, the RO aggregates the location (e.g., URL) where the physical resource can be accessed, while for the former the resource is physically uploaded to ROHub, which are stored in the selected storage. Currently ROHub supports S3 compatible object storages, such as Minio³¹, Ceph³², or the Amazon S3 Simple Storage Service³³.

²⁷ <http://vos.openlinksw.com/owiki/wiki/VOS>

²⁸ <https://www.researchobject.org/initiative/research-object-model/>

²⁹ <https://www.postgresql.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.elastic.co/>

³¹ <https://min.io/>

³² <https://ceph.io/en/>

³³ https://aws.amazon.com/s3/?did=ft_card&trk=ft_card

Each ROHub instance has its own resource storage. ROHub development instance currently uses a Minio service deployed at PSNC, while ROHub production uses Amazon S3.

As part of the future work, ROHub will:

- Integrate and support B2Drop as the default resource storage using the user's credentials (via the user token). Note that in this case, the storage limits for the user account in B2Drop will apply, and the internal resources size will count towards this limit. Also, if the user reaches his limit in B2Drop, he won't be able to store any additional internal resources.
- Allow the user to select the default storage for internal resources, so that he can choose B2Drop or one of the available S3 storages.

7.5 ROHub middleware services

ROHub application is deployed in a PaaS (Platform as a Service) environment, and relies on different middleware services enabling communication and execution of jobs. These include:

- Celery³⁴: an asynchronous task queue that is based on distributed message passing. This service is used by ROHub to carry out time consuming operations asynchronously like importing research objects, or creating snapshots, archives and forks. Celery also includes the celery beat, which is a scheduler that kicks off tasks at regular intervals that are executed by available worker nodes in the cluster. Examples of these tasks include: refreshing the index of research objects, activities and statistics, calculating size of internal resources, and the execution of enrichment and stability services. Celery requires a solution to send and receive messages; usually this comes in the form of a separate service called a message broker. In the case of ROHub, this broker is RabbitMQ.
- RabbitMQ³⁵: the message broker used by Celery in ROHub.

7.6 External services

ROHub integrates and leverages different external services, including the following RO added value services:

- Checklist service (described in Section 5). This service functionality will be available from both ROHub interfaces (Portal and Python library). The ongoing implementation in Portal looks similar to the previous portal (as depicted in the figure below), but includes actions buttons that allows the user to complement/fix the research object to comply with the checklist requirements.

³⁴ <https://docs.celeryproject.org/en/stable/index.html>

³⁵ <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

Figure 12 checklist service interface in ROHub (mock-up)

- Quality monitoring service (described in Section 5). This service will be also available from the ROHub portal and Python library (in a simplified way). The ROHub portal will show some graphical representation of the research object quality history along with the quality values (completeness, stability, reliability), while the library will show only the quality values. The implementation is still in design phase.
- Enrichment service (described in deliverable D3.2). This service functionality will be also available from the ROHub portal and Python library. From both interfaces, the user will be able to call the service on demand to enrich (or update previous enrichment) the research object. As described in deliverable D3.2, this service will be called automatically by ROHub for new/updated research objects at certain periods of time, but the user can force the enrichment to execute it immediately. Additionally, the annotations generated by the service are displayed in the portal in the research object overview page. The component shows the annotations in different color depending on the type of annotation, as depicted in figure below.

PUBLIC
IMPORTED
ARCHIVE
WORKFLOW-CENTRIC RESEARCH OBJECT

DOI: 10.24424/RO-ID.HRFPNERWFQ

☆ 0.00 / 5
💬 0
❤️ 0

Created: 18 October 2019 (15:33)

Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM

Elisa Trasatti
 Last modified: 07 December 2021 (09:34)
 Imported: 07 December 2021 (09:34) (Archived: 18 October 2019 (15:33))

Description:

The VSM (Volcano and Seismic source Modelling) tool is a Fortran code used to model ground deformation detected by the most common geodetic techniques (interferometric SAR, GPS, leveling and EDM - Electro-optical Distance Measuring). VSM performs geophysical inversion modeling of ground deformation to retrieve the parameters of the causative magmatic source, or to retrieve the seismic source parameters. A magmatic source can be approximated (modeled) by a confined part of crust with a certain shape (e.g., a sphere, a sill, a dyke, a spheroid), which is inflating/deflating because of a change in...

[Show more >](#)

Sketch:

(Source: Galland, 2012)

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QUALITY 0%

KEYWORDS:

LEGEND:

- PERSONS
- DOMAINS
- FREQUENT EXPRESSION
- PLACES
- ORGANIZATIONS
- CONCEPTS

DISCOVERED METADATA: ⓘ

VOLCANOLOGY
GEOMETRY
VSM TOOL
INVERSION CORE
TOOL
INVERSION
SHAPE
DEFORMATION
SOURCE

0	
Downloads	Views
Hide more details	
Resources	22
Annotations	71
Events	1
Forks	0
Snapshots	0
Archives	0
Size	2922.86 KB

Figure 13 Enrichment annotations displayed in ROHub portal

- PDF service: A simple service that generates a paper style representation of the research object in PDF format. The service will be available to scientists and other users from both the ROHub portal and the library, providing them the possibility to download the research object as a PDF (as depicted in the figure below).

Sketch:

(Source: Galland, 2012)

[Show more >](#)

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Małgorzata Wolniewicz
Importer

QUALITY 0%

KEYWORDS:

GEODETTIC DATA **VOLCANO DEFORMATION**
SOURCE MODEL **MAGMATIC SOURCE**

DISCOVERED METADATA: ⓘ

VOLCANOLOGY **GEOMETRY** **VSM TOOL**
INVERSION CORE **TOOL** **INVERSION**
SHAPE **DEFORMATION** **SOURCE**

TOOLBOX

Download
Metadata
ZIP
PDF

Elisa Trasatti. "Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM." ROHub. Oct 18, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.24424/ro-id.HRFPNERWFQ>.

LOCATION:

CONTENT

- biblio
 - produced
 - used
- config

Figure 14 PDF service functionality from ROHub portal

A partial view of the generated PDF is provided in the figure below

Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM

Elisa Trasatti

Abstract—The VSM (Volcano and Seismic source Modelling) tool is a Fortran code used to model ground deformation detected by the most common geodetic techniques (interferometric SAR, GPS, leveling and EDM - Electro-optical Distance Measuring). VSM performs geophysical inversion modeling of ground deformation to retrieve the parameters of the causative magmatic source, or to retrieve the seismic source parameters. A magmatic source can be approximated (modeled) by a confined part of crust with a certain shape (e.g., a sphere, a sill, a dyke, a spheroid), which is inflating/deflating because of a change in the internal magma/gas pressure. Each shape generates a specific surface deformation pattern, and comparing the modeled deformation with that actually observed at the surface, it is possible to estimate the best-fit source parameters. The same applies to the seismic source, that is commonly described as a rectangular plane with dip and strike angles. The VSM tool carries out this task by minimizing the difference between the observed and the computed displacement field, through a global optimization process. The VSM tool allows the user to choose among several geometrical sources: sphere (Mogi, 1958), spheroid (Yang et al., 1988), ellipsoid (Davis, 1986), fault (Okada, 1992), sill-like source (Fialko et al., 2001) and retrieves the best-fit source parameters. More sources can be combined. The VSM software tool is developed by INGV, in Fortran 90. The non-linear inversion core is by M. Sambridge (1999). This Research Object contains the OSX and Linux executables, documentation and input/output if a real example applied to Campi Flegrei (Italy) with InSAR and GPS data. Please refer to documentation for further information. Contact: Elisa Trasatti elisa.trasatti@ingv.it.

Keywords—volcano deformation, magmatic source, source model, geodetic data, volcanology, geometry, VSM tool, inversion core, inversion, shape, tool, deformation, Source

I. INTRODUCTION

This document provides a paper-style view of the Research Object (RO) *Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM*¹ which is a *ARCHIVE*.

The RO research area is: *Earth sciences* and is of type ². An overview of this RO is depicted in Figure ??.

Figure 15 Partial view of a research object in PDF format

- Note that the ADAM Data Cube service (described in deliverable D4.2) exposes EO Data Cubes, which can be aggregated and described in the research object (using the metadata models described in D4.1, D5.1).

Additionally, ROHub integrates and leverages the following EOSC services:

- EGI check-in (described in Section 7.2)
- Zenodo (described in Section 6). As described in Section 6, users are able to publish snapshots/archives of research objects in Zenodo and/or B2Share. This functionality is available from both the portal and library as part of the evolution mechanisms. In portal, for example, the user can generate a snapshot/archive from the source research object overview page (using the third button in the toolbox as depicted figure below).

TABLE I
RESEARCH OBJECT RESOURCES

Name	Type	Creation time
³ Fialko 2001	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
⁴ None	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
⁵ Davis 1986	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
⁶ Yang, Davis and Dieterich	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
⁷ Neighbourhood Algorithm - I	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
⁸ Campi Flegrei (Italy) 2004-20...	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
⁹ Neighbourhood Algorithm - II	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
¹⁰ Campi Flegrei (Italy) 2011-20...	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
¹¹ None	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
¹² Santorini (Greece) unres	Bibliographic Resource	2021-12-07 08:34:04
VSM_input_example.zip	Dataset	2021-12-07 08:34:07
VSM_data_example.zip	Dataset	2021-12-07 08:34:08
HOW_TO_USE_VSM.pdf	Document	2021-12-07 08:34:07
description.rtf	Document	2021-12-07 08:34:05
VSM_MacOS_10.14	File	2021-12-07 08:34:09
VSM_RedHat_6.7	File	2021-12-07 08:34:06
VSM_example.zip	File	2021-12-07 08:34:07
VSM_ubuntu20.04	File	2021-12-07 08:34:09
VSM_ubuntu12.04	File	2021-12-07 08:34:08
¹³ Santorini (Greece) post unres...	Paper	2021-12-07 08:34:04
VSM_results_example.zip	Result	2021-12-07 08:34:05
galland-eps1-2012-figura-2.jp...	Sketch	2021-12-07 08:34:06

III. RELATED LOCATIONS

This Research Object has the following geospatial locations associated:

- <https://api.rohub.org/api/annotations/07c24785-5f1a-441f-a4dd-ef630e0847/download/>
- <https://api.rohub.org/api/annotations/0e331288-f31b-45ef-b863-a791656d045e/download/>
- <https://api.rohub.org/api/annotations/0ef3103c-4c5a-4d13-a8d8-8a8ee3875106/download/>
- <https://api.rohub.org/api/annotations/48a18e40-6d8c-4fa8-81df-5cfb29325557/download/>

Figure 16 Evolution mechanisms from ROHub portal

Selecting any of the evolution options (fork, snapshot, archive) will open the create RO wizard, customized to the state selected. In the case of selecting snapshot/archive, the wizard gives the possibility to generate a DOI, and to publish it in Zenodo/B2Share (as depicted in the figure below).

From the library, the user can use the method snapshot or archive from the current research object. Both methods accept four optional parameters:

- title: if none is provided, the source RO title is used appended with suffix string “-snapshot”
- description: if none is provided, uses the same description as in the source RO
- create_doi: flag by default is False.
- publication_services: name of the service to publish the snapshot/archive. The current accepted values are Zenodo, B2Share.

The screenshot shows the ROHub portal interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with eight items: Basic information, Authors & contributors, Tags, Sketches gallery, Resources, Related locations, License & Funding, and Other metadata. Below the menu, the 'Basic information' section is active, displaying the title 'Volcano and Seismic source Modelling VSM'. The description section follows, containing a detailed text about the VSM tool. Below the description, there are options for 'Publication services' (No Needed, B2SHARE, ZENODO) and a 'Create DOI' checkbox. At the bottom, there are three buttons: 'Snapshot & Exit', 'Reset form', and 'Snapshot & Go to overview'.

Figure 17 Creating a snapshot from a research object from ROHub portal

- B2Share (described in Section 6). Same as previous point.
- B2Drop (described in Section 7.4) . This functionality is in progress.
- Note that the python library allows using ROHub from EGI Notebooks, which is the default work and computing environment used by researchers in RELIANCE.

7.7 ROHub Portal

The ROHub portal is a Web client application providing a comprehensive user interface for the management and preservation of research objects (ROs). A new portal has been created as part of RELIANCE project, taking into account all the feedback received over the years about the previous portal, and using a more modern stack of technologies which can be easily maintained and extended. In particular, the new ROHub portal was developed using React³⁶, JavaScript library for building user interfaces based on UI components. In RELIANCE there are two instances of ROHub portal: the production instance has deployed the latest stable version of the portal and uses the production instance of ROHub backend and IAM, while the development instance has deployed the ongoing additions/updates that are being tested before moving them to a stable version and uses the development instance of ROHub backend and IAM.

The portal is available at:

- <https://reliance.rohub.org/> (production). (see screenshot below)
- <https://rohub2020-rohub.apps.paas-dev.psnc.pl/> (development)

³⁶ <https://reactjs.org/>

A full user guide for the ROHub portal is available at <https://reliance-eosc.github.io/rohub-portal-documentation/> (ongoing).

7.8 ROHub Python Library

RELIANCE also produced an ROHub Python library, providing a user-friendly API for working with research objects. The Python API works on top of the ROHub backed REST API, wrapping and abstracting the REST methods in user friendly API methods. One of the main goals for this library was to enable users to work with research objects directly from Jupyter Notebooks, which is the main working and computing environment in RELIANCE.

The Package is distributed through Python Package Index (PyPI), and so it can be installed easily by typing: ***pip install rohub***

A full documentation of the ROHub library API is available at: <https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API-documentation/html/index.html> (see snippet in Table 3). The library is distributed as open source code under an MIT license and is available from PSNC code repository³⁷.

Table 4 API python library documentation example (research object creation)

```
rohub.ros_create(title, research_areas, description=None, access_mode=None, ros_type=None, template=None, owner=None, editors=None, readers=None, creation_mode=None)
```

Function that creates new research object in the API and instantiates a Python object that can be reused. See also:

```
list_valid_research_areas()
```

```
list_valid_access_modes()
```

```
list_valid_ros_types()
```

```
list_valid_templates()
```

```
list_valid_creation_modes()
```

Note

The newly created research object will return a Python object that has its own set of methods and attributes. You may want to assign it to a variable to make it easy to work with. For example: `my_ros = ros_create(**your set of params)`

Parameters

- title (*str*) – title of your research object
- research_areas (*list*) – research areas associated with your research object
- description (*str*) – description of your research object, optional
- access_mode (*str*) – research object's access mode, optional
- ros_type (*str*) – research object's type, optional
- template (*str*) – research object's template, optional
- owner (*str*) – research object's owner, optional
- editors (*list*) – research object's editors, optional
- readers (*list*) – research object's readers, optional
- creation_mode (*str*) – research object's creation mode, optional

Returns

³⁷ <https://git.man.poznan.pl/stash/projects/ROHUB/repos/rohub-api/browse?at=refs%2Fheads%2Fmaster>

newly created research object
Return type: [ResearchObject](#)

A demo Jupyter Notebook showcasing (most of) the library method is available at: <https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/sample-notebooks/blob/main/ROHub-library-prod-demo.ipynb> (see Figure 17). This and other sample Jupyter Notebooks are available in GitHub project sample-notebooks (of RELIANCE-EOSC organization)³⁸.

³⁸ <https://github.com/RELIANCE-EOSC/sample-notebooks/>

```

Import library

In [ ]:
import rohub

Authenticate

In [ ]:
rohub_user = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-user").read().rstrip()
rohub_pwd = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-pwd").read().rstrip()
rohub.login(username=rohub_user, password=rohub_pwd)
#rohub_client_id = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-client_id").read().rstrip()
#rohub_client_secret = open("/home/jovyan/files/rohub-client_secret").read().rstrip()
#rohub.login(client_id=rohub_client_id, client_secret=rohub_client_secret)

RO methods

Create new RO

In [ ]:
ro_title="8th December - Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service Data Cube Research Object"
ro_research_areas=["Earth sciences"]
ro_description="This Research Object demonstrate how to compute monthly map of PM10 over your country"
ro_ros_type="Data-centric Research Object"
ro_ros_template="Data Centric Research Object folders structure"

ro = rohub.ros_create(title=ro_title, research_areas=ro_research_areas, description=ro_description, ros_type=ro_ros_type, template=ro_ros_

Find ROs

In [ ]:
rohub.ros_find(search="December")

List my ROs

In [ ]:
myros=rohub.list_my_ros()
myros[0:10]

```

Figure 18 Snippet of the demo Jupyter Notebook showcasing ROHub library

8 Conclusions

This document describes the results and current status of the initial version of the tools and services for Research Objects (ROs) management, resulting from the WP5 tasks, including the services for FAIR assessment and quality assessment of research objects, the adaptations of research objects evolution to EOSC scenarios, the initial integration of services from WP3 and WP4, and the current state of the user interfaces.

Regarding the FAIR assessment of research objects, the approach has been defined and relevant tools have been identified. Assessing the FAIRness of a research object would be a composite measurement that involves not only assessing the object itself but also the resources it aggregates. The identified tools will be used as starting point and/or inspiration for the service implementation. The service will use ro-crate as the default format for input research objects and it will be integrated with ROHub.

Regarding the quality assessment, an initial version of the services for RELIANCE have been deployed, by extending and adapting existing tools. These include the checklist service which assess the research object quality according to what the research communities producing and reusing them consider relevant and the quality monitoring that assess different quality metrics over time, including completeness, stability, and reliability. The services are currently being integrated into ROHub, and the future work involves facilitating the creation and customization of checklists.

Also, after describing the architecture of the ROHub research object management platform, the document describes how the external services are being integrated including those previously mentioned and other research object added-value services (e.g., enrichment described in D3.2), as well as other EOSC services. Finally, the document describes the user interfaces of ROHub providing the links to the documentation and user guides.

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